

CIRCULAR SPRINT Playbook

Yannick Christiaens, Francesca Ostuzzi & Louise Dumon (Ghent University)

Tuomas Puttonen (Aalto University)

Phillip Wallat (TU Clausthal)

Nicola Doppio (Hub Innovazione Trentino)

Wim Van Opstal (VITO)

Edited by Tuomas Puttonen

ABSTRACT

The Circular sPrint format was developed by the CRAFTH project consortium which organized a total of four Circular sPrints events during 2020 and 2021, amidst the global Covid19 pandemic. The event was a modified version of a Design Sprint and its core goal was to increase the sustainability of physical products and services via design thinking, aided by novel manufacturing technologies, namely additive manufacturing.

This document, the “Circular sPrint Playbook” is a collection of know-how, experiences, and digital documents that the consortium wants to share with anyone wishing to re-create or draw inspiration from a *Circular sPrint* event. We also discuss how the program was adapted, due to the pandemic, from a physical event to a virtual event in 2020, and how the format was modified as a hybrid implementation in 2021.

We want to offer our appreciation for the project funding. The CRAFTH-project was funded over a 2-year period by the RawMaterials Academy which is the overarching brand of all the education activities of the [EIT RawMaterials](#).

CONSORTIUM

The CRAFTH consortium is a collaboration between universities and research institutions across Europe. This alliance dates back to 2019 when the EIT RawMaterials launched the KAVA Call 6. The design.nexus research group of Ghent university was in search for partners to develop an event format which would challenge and educate PhD students, professional designers and companies, coming from a wide background, in combining Additive Manufacturing technologies (AM) and Circular Design (CD).

The EIT RawMaterials network provided partners with deep thematic knowledge on sustainability, additive manufacturing, and the organisation of innovation challenges. With the financial support of EIT RawMaterials & the EIT Raw materials academy, the CRAFTH consortium was able to develop Circular sPrint.

Project Partners:

Ghent university - design.nexus research group ([link](#)) - The UGent design.nexus research group based in Campus Kortrijk is dedicated to create bridges between education, sustainability and industry in the field of technology-driven design and processes of innovative product/service and consumption/production systems. The group implements interdisciplinary design strategies and best practices together with industry and organisations from both public and private sectors.

Aalto university ([link](#)) - ADDLAB, Aalto University Digital Design Laboratory, is a research organization initiated by the Aalto University's School of Engineering and School of Arts, Design and Architecture.

TU Clausthal ([link](#)) - Institute of Materials Science and Engineering.

Hub Innovazione Trentino ([link](#)) - Promotes the results of scientific research in Trentino through technology transfer activities to private companies and investors. Stimulates a set of formats and education processes **to promote entrepreneurship** among master and PHD students and researchers as well as new business creation coming from local research ecosystem.

VITO ([link](#)) - VITO is an independent Flemish research organisation in the area of cleantech and sustainable development with the goal to accelerate the transition to a sustainable world.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A Global Shift Towards a Sustainable Society

The 21st Century global environmental and socio-economic issues have, for decades, been recognized to hinder our ability to meet “*the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs*” (WCED, 1987, p. 43)¹. A widespread societal transition to sustainability should happen to balance the situation. A sustainable development is the compilation of possible pathways that point towards sustainability as a desired future *objective*. The objective has been recently represented by 17 global sustainable development goals (SDG, UN, 2015; sdgs.un.org)² related to economy, society, and environment. These three areas should be seen as integrated and *nested* into one another. Finally, **sustainability today becomes a decision-guiding objective** for several actors and can be seen as a system property, rising from the interaction of different actors, rules, technologies, and infrastructures.

However, it is not clear how exactly *sustainable societies* should look like. Therefore, **the role and interplay of design and technology becomes critical**. On the one hand, design is a discipline capable of potentially supporting others by tackling complex, unstable, and often conflictual realities. Cross (2001)³ and Rittel (1973)⁴ refer to them as *wicked* realities. On the other hand, industrial design is considered responsible for creation and diffusion of unsustainable production-consumption patterns – “there are professions more harmful than industrial design, but only a very few of them” (Papanek, 1973, p. ix)⁵. Therefore, **the role of design should be taken into account in its dual responsibility. Design is influenced by – and itself influences – bigger socio-technical systems** (Hopwood et al., 2005)⁶. If design can imagine and even facilitate that-which-does-not-yet-exist,

¹ World Commission on Environmental Development. (1987). Our common future. Oxford, England: Oxford University Press.

² SDG, UN, 2015, THE 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development (un.org)

³ Cross, N. (2001). Designerly ways of knowing: Design discipline versus design science. *Design issues*, 17(3), 49-55.

⁴ Rittel, H.W.J., Webber, M.M. Dilemmas in a general theory of planning. *Policy Sci* 4, 155–169 (1973). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01405730>

⁵ Papanek, V., & Fuller, R. B. (1972). Design for the real world.

⁶ Hopwood, B., Mellor, M., & O'Brien, G. (2005). Sustainable development: mapping different approaches. *Sustainable development*, 13(1), 38-52.

Design for Sustainability specifically focuses on outlining actions and tools that have the potential to bring the societal transitions in line with the 17 UN sustainability development goals (Ceschin, 2014)⁷.

The Role of Design in Sustainability

But what is design, precisely? Design is the process of creation of what does not yet exist. In this view, design can be defined as a generative and solution-oriented activity that aims at improving our reality by proposing tangible outcomes. The typical design process is iterative, and continuously shifts between understanding the problem, defining possible solutions, developing and exploring them through experiments, and finally delivering them. When a designer develops and explores solutions, a hands-on approach is often welcome: in this approach the designer strongly relies on sketches, visualizations, narratives, etc. to express his/hers/their ideas. These prototypes can be considered a fundamental aspect of the design process, as they help designers develop solutions and - more importantly - communicate and test their ideas with others, to verify their relevance. On a systemic design level, the Circular Economy (CE) concept provides one approach towards a more sustainable society. The concept promotes economic systems where products and services are traded in closed loops or 'cycles'. It can be viewed also as a philosophy of resource efficiency. It is important to note that CE does not reject the for-profit capitalistic ideal. It only introduces sustainability into the equation as a core objective and attempts to highlight that sustainable processes and actions can also foster business and added monetary value. Regenerative by design, CE aims to create and retain as much economic and societal value as possible of products, parts, and materials throughout their whole lifecycle. To reach these goals, several circular strategies can be applied:

- Smarter product use and manufacturing (Refuse, Rethink, and Reduce)
- Extend lifespan of products and their parts (Re-use, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, and Repurpose)
- Retain the value of raw materials (Recycle, and Recover)

Circular strategies are not applied solely because of environmental and societal concerns. To have resilient and sustainable circular business models, circular strategies must enhance the business value proposition of a product or service. Value creation is the key, because only a limited number of parties are interested in circular products because of their circularity alone.

⁷ Ceschin, F. (2014). How the design of socio-technical experiments can enable radical changes for sustainability. *International Journal of Design*, 8(3), 1-21

The Role of Technology in Sustainability

The role of design was discussed in relation to a sustainable society of the future. Yet the role of technological progress is equally important. The CRAFTH consortium decided to select manufacturing technologies as a focus area for the *Circular sPrint* event. The modern lifestyle, business, and consumer goods are products of the manufacturing sector and widely responsible for a great share of the global energy and resource use. In addition, this choice is also directly relatable to the general public via consumerism and as an example of new technology facilitated by design. Emerging manufacturing technologies, such as Additive Manufacturing (AM), can help achieve sustainability goals. The AM layer-by-layer manufacturing method minimizes material use and provides designers with more freedom to increase sustainability in the products by design. Initially invented and used for prototyping in the mid-1980s, AM technology has matured astonishingly fast. Early on, it became an integrated part of prototyping. Currently, AM technologies are increasingly applied in direct manufacturing of end-products (Thompson et al., 2016)⁸.

AM provides many possibilities that link together well with the circular economy (Sauerwein et al., 2019)⁹. There is a distinctive trend towards digitalization in design and manufacturing. AM enables distributed, toolless manufacturing that may render warehouses stacked with spare parts a thing of the past. Started in the early 20th century, and accelerated by globalization, the mass production ideology of Henry Ford has been engineered to perfection. Manufacturing of identical products in very high volumes may be energy efficient – yet can also promote overconsumption and unnecessary stock, and valuable materials, ending up as waste. The Ellen MacArthur Foundation circular economy diagram¹⁰ defines product repair and life span prolongation as a first, and preferred, step to manage the continuous flow of technical materials. Production of durable, customized products to order rather than to anticipated demand is a more sustainable approach. The ability of AM to customize each product and optimize their repairability is an asset in paving the way back to products that are designed to last for generations.

AM was selected as a focus technology also for another reason. The availability of affordable manufacturing hardware and free software resources for the average consumer have led to the *democratization of manufacturing*, meaning that **anyone** can become a designer, and that **anyone**

⁸ Thompson, M.K., Moroni, G., Vaneker, T., Fadel, G., Campbell, R.I., Gibson, I., Bernard, A., Schulz, J., Graf, P., Ahuja, B. and Martina, F., 2016. Design for Additive Manufacturing: Trends, opportunities, considerations, and constraints. *CIRP annals*, 65(2), pp.737-760.

⁹ Sauerwein, M., Doubrovski, E., Balkenende, R. and Bakker, C., 2019. Exploring the potential of additive manufacturing for product design in a circular economy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 226, pp.1138-1149.

¹⁰ <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-economy-diagram>

can manufacture their own designs. The barrier is lower than ever for individuals to make conscious decisions and to become an active party in the pursuit for a more sustainable future for us all.

CRAFTH project consortium and the *Circular sPrint* event were created for that purpose. We want to harness and promote the positive impact of **design and technology in solving the global unsustainability problem**. Our approach with the event was to specifically target doctoral researchers from varying research fields and educate the participants to sustainable design thinking. This approach maximizes the technology and design thinking transfer into the research community. A hands-on design sprint was chosen as a format as it can help provide tangible solutions and promote multidisciplinary work within a compact timeframe.

A Design Sprint as a Facilitator

The Design Sprint is a five-phase process for applying design thinking techniques to find solutions to business and product development problems through ideation, prototyping, and testing ideas with customers (Figure 1). The Sprint was developed at GV - Former Google ventures, a startup incubator and accelerator from Alphabet, with the purpose of effectively fostering product development and innovation in startups in the digital industry¹¹.

Figure 1. The five phases of a Design Sprint

¹¹ Knapp, J., Zeratsky, J., & Kowitz, B. (2016). *Sprint: How to Solve Big Problems and Test New Ideas in Just Five Days*.

In the Design Sprint a strong emphasis is given to analyzing the problem to be solved, also envisioning a future scenario where the designed solution (whatever it will be) is able to bring about the expected impacts. This drives the following phases of the Sprint, which include a structured decision process (which is normally not proposed in other design thinking frameworks) as well as prototype testing with end users. The Design Sprint is normally carried out over a 5-day period by the product development team, involving designers, engineers, product managers, marketing and sales, possibly with the support of a facilitator.

For the Circular sPrint we modified the Design Sprint format to better suit our purposes. The event was deployed in more than 5 days with teams of mostly PhD students, though in strict cooperation with a company or other challenge owner, who provides the design problem and context. Educational content was added to familiarize the participants with the circular economy concept and additive manufacturing. The circularity of the design was added as a key objective.

The next chapter, “Making of a Circular sPrint”, will present the practicalities of organizing a Circular sPrint. We begin by unwrapping event planning, continue to varying preparation activities, and finally discuss the implementation of the event itself. In the final chapter, the general experiences, and learnings from the CRAFTH project are summarized. Finally, we discuss how similar innovation initiatives could become economically independent and continue their life independently once a dedicated project comes to an end.

2. MAKING OF A CIRCULAR SPRINT

The “Making of a Circular Sprint”- chapter presents the steps and practicalities of organizing a design sprint from the primary event planning all the way to event execution. The following subchapters discuss the most important activities in more detail.

Throughout the text we refer to files created as part of the CRAFTH-project and the Circular sPrint events. These documents are published (open access) in an online repository for anyone to use or draw inspiration from. The list of digital appendices is provided in chapter 4. All files can be accessed through the DOI identifier: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6327728>

Event Timeline

We begin by presenting an overall timeline of the Circular sPrint 2021 events and their preparations. Depending on the scale and format of the event, pre-activities can take anywhere from 6 to more than 12 months. Figure 2 presents an approximate timeline of activities, dates, important milestones, and deadlines identified for the Circular sPrint events held 7-17 September 2021. A similar Gantt- chart is recommended for overall planning of activities and distribution of tasks between the organizing members.

Figure 2. A cropped version of a Gantt-chart of activities leading to the Circular sPrint events 7-17 September 2021. The full PDF is available in the data repository.

After the event format is defined, attracting participants and companies (and/or sponsors) becomes the main objective. This process takes time and requires marketing, numerous company inquiries, and meetings. The conversion rate of inquiries into actual company cooperation might be in the range of 10-30%. Similarly, the attendance rate of registered participants is known to fall between 50-70%. These numbers are good to keep in mind when estimating the required number of registrations to reach a target participant count and needed time to allocate for company cooperation and sponsorship discussions. Also keep in mind that people from the consortium (as well as company representatives, and participants) have different schedules and life situations. Remember to take national holidays and the school or university annual calendar into account in scheduling. Meetings in the consortium should be well-planned, follow a clear agenda, and only involve the necessary people. Once initial responsibilities are divided, it is more efficient for the organizing group to divide into smaller task groups. The dedicated task groups can meet more frequently. The whole consortium should meet only when necessary to update on the overall completion rate of individual tasks and agree on the next steps.

Some milestones in event preparations also act as natural bottlenecks for further process steps. The start of the registration period being the first. Before that, the event format should be defined, website made operational, participant registration form ready, and the first batch of marketing material created. Naturally, an operational website early on helps attract companies and sponsors to take part in the event. Preparation of the lecture content and tools for the event can then progress mostly in the background, regardless of other activities.

Event Definition

2.2.1. Mission Statement, Goals & Event Format

A Circular sPrint is ultimately an Open Innovation initiative¹² that allows companies (or other institutions, including public bodies) to improve and innovate products and services in a circular way and with the use of additive manufacturing by means of engaging with young talents coming from outside those organizations.

When designing an Open Innovation initiative, especially within a competitive setting (e.g., a *hackathon*), a specific canvas can be used by the organizers: the *Innovation Challenge Design Canvas*, which allow to identify what are the main aspects that need to be devised and managed to set up and launch an Innovation Challenge. In the filled canvas below, we provide a snapshot description of the Circular sPrint.

¹² Doppio, N., Väinämö, S., & Haukipuro, L. (2020). Design elements of innovation contests supporting Open Innovation in SMEs - An action research study. *Journal of Innovation Management*, 8(4), 26–56.

Figure 3. The Circular sPrint format in a nutshell, described as an Open Innovation Challenge¹³.

In the following paragraph we expand on each of the twelve blocks of the above canvas (Figure 3).

- **Goal.** Goal of the Circular sPrint is twofold: on one side, to support companies in designing more circular products; on the other side, to train students in exploiting additive manufacturing to increase product circularity.
- **Seekers.** Seekers are the companies or other institutions (e.g., public bodies) that would like to exploit additive manufacturing to increase circularity of a product and/or a service. Normally they are manufacturing or design companies.
- **Challenge.** The challenge is the problem that the seekers wish to solve by taking part in the Circular sPrint. Normally it regards a specific product or a service, its performance, or its production process (including the full material lifecycle, end-of-life, and waste).

¹³ <https://www.innochallenge-project.eu/>

- **Solutions.** The solutions delivered by a Circular sPrint can be new product ideas, concepts, prototypes (e.g., 3D CAD), designs (e.g., technical specifications, 3D CAD files), or validations through user tests with an increased circularity. The learning process of the stakeholders is also one of the core outcomes. However, it is harder to measure.
- **Activities.** The Circular sPrint comes in the form of a 1 or 2-week Design Sprint, where teams compete (and partially collaborate) with each other to solve the presented challenges.
- **Solvers.** They take part in the event as participants and attempt to provide a solution to a given challenge. Solvers may be students (PhD, MSc and BSc) and/or industry professionals. They are mentored by design and additive manufacturing professionals during the event. Solvers normally take part in the sPrint as a non-curricular activity. However, ECTS credits may be recognized by universities and can increase the event attractiveness for students.
- **Incentives.** Solvers are motivated because they can learn how to employ additive manufacturing to boost circularity of real products and services, furthermore the interdisciplinary networking (also intended between academics and industries) should not be underestimated. Seekers are motivated because they can source ideas and prototype solutions to innovate products and services.
- **Timeline.** The time allocation for preparations is dependent on the chosen format and the desired number of solvers and challenges. 1 or 2 weeks of execution of the Circular sPrint; 2-2 months of promotion of the opportunity to both seekers and solvers; 4 months of preparation by organizers, along with partners; 2 weeks of debriefing (delivering certificates, gathering feedback, and evaluating the event, etc.). An example timeline of activities is provided as an appendix.
- **Governance.** The Circular sPrint can be organized by universities, research centers, business support agencies and/or technology transfer agencies. In principle, it could also be organized by a (large) company. However, the involvement of all these stakeholders is normally required to get to a successful event.
- **Business Model.** Seekers may be required to pay a fee to retain the intellectual property rights (IPR) of results, while the initiative is normally free for solvers. It's good to have an external funding (e.g., public grants) source to cover personnel costs. Creating a volunteer-based organization may help in project continuity.
- **IPR - Intellectual Property Rights.** IPR is normally retained by seekers to maximize and simplify exploitation of results. Otherwise, the IPR may be retained by the solvers, to support the launch of startups or spinoffs. The development of at least one open-source solution during an event is encouraged. This solution can serve as a publishable demonstrator and help attract solvers and seekers in the next event editions.
- **Regulations.** Call for applications to select seekers and solvers may be required in case the organizer operates under public law.

2.2.2. Managing Expectations

All individual participants and company representatives will have their own personal idea of what the event will be about and what they expect to achieve at the end of it. This idea might be completely different from the expectations you, as an organizer, hoped to achieve. Especially without prior experience as an event organizer, it is hard to deliver an event that matches with the intended format and event goals. Yet, delivering a successful event necessitates you either fulfill prior goals and expectations OR provide something unexpected that will nevertheless satisfy participants.

Creation and understanding of expectations are based mostly on the content and communication between the organizers and prospective participants. For that reason, the website content should be made as clear and truthful as possible, from the start. Same goes for marketing. Participants might expect, for example, to learn theory, new skills, teamwork, and obtain new contacts. Companies might want to improve their products, gain new insights, business cases, or identify talented future workforce. It is not unheard of that people will attend an event solely out of curiosity, because of credits (students), or simply to meet people. An organizer can try to elicit these personal expectations before the start of the event. After initial interest is created, directly ask the company representatives: “What do you wish to accomplish by participating in the event? What are your expectations?”. The participants can be asked to write their expectations in the application form, and later asked to verbalize their motivations during , for example, an intake interview. You might be surprised how different answers you will get. These valuable responses can help adjust the final event format.

What can be achieved in an event of only a week or two is often both overestimated and underestimated. The prior expectations are high and the challenge definitions of seekers might be overly complicated. It is advised to stay realistic and keep the challenges as simple as possible. Design is a form of experiential learning process. The primary outcome of the event is the learning process and exchange of ideas between all stakeholders. This should be made clear for all participants. A tangible prototype will be created to express the idea but it will, most definitely, require a continuation project (in the company) to develop into a proof-of-concept prototype. For both seekers and solvers, screening the aspects of circular economy can be an eye-opening exercise. It may allow the stakeholders to identify further innovation and business pathways in relation to a given challenge.

Challenges and Company Involvement

2.3.1. Getting in Touch with Companies

One of the initial things to be done to organize a Circular sPrint is to reach out to companies or other “solution seekers” that are interested in exploring the benefits of additive manufacturing to support circular design of products or services. Potential seekers can be manufacturing or service companies, design firms, public bodies, or entities (e.g., a city council, libraries, ...). However, we strongly recommend selecting specific products or services upon which additive manufacturing and circular design solutions can be applied.

The best way to approach companies is to first clarify the benefits of the Circular sPrint, stressing the fact that results will be tangible and further exploitable, and that the company will get in touch with young talented designers and engineers with whom they could establish fruitful collaborations. The conditions for participation shall also be clarified, for instance in terms of time and effort required by the companies in the execution of the Design Sprint (which entail some steps to be participated, or even led, by the companies). Along with that, depending on the regulations, companies may be required to pay an access fee that could be used by the organizer to cover costs such as prizes awarded to one or more winning teams, or other costs.

A call for applications to select companies may be required in case the organizer operates under public law, to abide with state aid regulations (the sPrint delivers significant added value to companies, and this support may indeed fall in the case of state aid if coming from a public entity). Nevertheless, after a first, informal contact, companies should fill in an application form, collecting information about the company, and, especially, the product or service to which they would like to apply to the Sprint (including pictures, link to online documentation, and possibly a 3D cad file).

Along with that, specific questions shall be included in the application form to understand what exactly is the challenge (problem or opportunity) that the company wishes to tackle. Examples of the challenges are the following: “*redesign an existing product and its assembled parts in a way to increase repairability*”. Face-to-face or online meetings with the company representatives are necessary to align expectations and finalize the challenges. The challenge definitions should preferably be public. If a company wishes, some information can be protected by a non-disclosure agreement (NDA) binding the organizers. The early moments are good for finding sponsors who

are willing to either financially support the event or provide 3D printers and print materials (in exchange, for example, of marketing visibility before and during the event).

A commission of experts may evaluate the applications, and finally select the most appropriate. Applications shall be evaluated using criteria such as challenge feasibility, potential business impact, potential social impact, circularity and so forth. It's good to introduce 3-6 challenges per event. Each challenge can be tackled by one or more teams: diversity adds value to the design process and makes the event more interesting for all stakeholders.

2.3.2. Defining Challenges & Company Agreement

We strongly recommend the organizer to have an agreement in place with the participating companies to regulate matters such as IPR - Intellectual Property Rights, non-disclosure of critical information, and, potentially, service levels (especially in case companies pay a fee), personal data management, and alike. The easiest way to handle this is to publish a call for selection of companies which also works as regulations of the initiatives (or "Terms and Conditions"). It is not strictly required that the organizer and the company sign an official agreement: indeed, a specific tick box can be included in the application form that asks the applicant company to accept the regulations of the initiative, acting as its "terms and conditions". If a distinct agreement is needed, an example is provided as part of the data package.

Once the companies are selected, the organizer shall get in touch with the companies to deepen the understanding of the selected cases. It is encouraged to devise a concise half-page description of the challenge, that will be afterwards shared with the solvers, and the mentors (coaches, or co-organizers). This short document will have to include all the information (including contact information), and links to other documentation, and acts as a unique touchpoint for the team to start the ideation during Circular sPrint.

Visual Communications & Marketing

2.4.1. Event Branding & Website

The established hackathons and innovation contests of today all share something in common. They have all started small and built their brand one event at a time. To attract participants year after year requires a good format to begin with. Yet, the role of marketing is extremely important, especially before the event brand has not yet been fully formed. Only when the event secures its

yearly position and a known brand can word-of-mouth marketing take over as the dominant (and free) yearly marketing base.

Circular sPrint was a completely new format developed from zero. In contrast to many other innovation contests and hackathons, the Circular sPrint differs in many aspects. The target audience is restricted to PhD students and industry professionals, the duration is weeks instead of a single weekend, and tangible 3D prints are strongly encouraged as prototypes. From the participant perspective, applying for a novel event without any clear reference points comes with a higher psychological barrier. Under this light, our suggestion is to use some familiar elements and terms when introducing the initiative, such as an “intensive course”, or an “extended hackathon”. Of course the format should be simple enough and clear to begin with.

Circular sPrint marketing started with the creation of a promotional website and an embedded application form for solvers, and, potentially, one for companies and other challenge owners. The website acts as the landing page for all marketing channels and must deliver all the necessary information for the prospective participants. As was seen in the timeline in Figure 2, the website must be set up at the latest a few months before the application form opens. This leaves time to do user testing on the website functions and ask feedback on the visuals.

Figure 4. The Circular sPrint website top banner.

In the case of Circular sPrint, the website navigation was split into the application, description of the event format, event practical information, and terms and conditions (Figure 4). It is also good to provide a contact form for interested participants as well as companies who would wish to join the event with a challenge, or as sponsors. Pay attention that the final website is both logical and visually appealing. A website with an unfinished feeling can damage the brand and even discourage

participants from applying. A full, static reference version of the Circular sPrint website can be viewed for reference as part of the data package (4. Digital Appendices). In the best-case scenario, the whole event brand is tied together with the graphic design of the website, marketing material, and any visuals shown during the event. If possible, a graphic designer is highly recommended. However, building a cohesive visual brand for an event is not the crucial concern for a first-time event. The priority is to deliver an enjoyable event that provides value for participants, is a proof-of-concept that the format works. The first event iteration gathers valuable intel what aspects of the event worked and whether the format has potential for further continuation.

Figure 5. Example marketing layout for social media channels.

2.4.2. Marketing Channels

The selection of marketing channels should be based on the target group. In our case it was PhD students and professionals. The most successful strategy to reach PhD's was found to be simply through a university email list of doctoral candidates. A visual, one-page PDF document is a good e-mail attachment that crystallizes the event information (example available in the data package). Targeting a few large Universities can reach thousands with a rather small effort. In fact, approximately 80% of Circular sPrint participants found the event based on email marketing. Still, a multichannel marketing strategy is favorable for maximizing visibility. Regional, or EU-level portals that collect students, organizations, and universities can reach a way bigger audience. Local student

unions or associations can be used to reinforce the message. Social media marketing via the University and partner channels may be used concurrently.

The strategy to attract professional participants and company challenges is different. Professional social media platforms such as LinkedIn, or Twitter may work best. The campaign can initiate with a generic ad when the event application opens (Figure 5). Once the event challenges are agreed with the companies, they can be included in the marketing as seen in Figure 6.

An additional strategy to gain visibility is to cooperate with cluster organizations, or other entities that share the same thematic goals with the event. The Circular sPrint event was kindly marketed through Aalto Design Factory channels as the two share an interest in promoting cross-disciplinary product development. Another example of this type of marketing took place through the Finnish Rapid Prototyping Association and Fame3D. These two organizations gather the professional as well as hobbyist 3D printing community of Finland. Thematic groups for example on LinkedIn, and Facebook can be additional ways to spread the word.

Figure 6. Challenge cards can be used in marketing once the challenge definitions have been agreed with the seekers.

Despite the multiple channels for professionals, the professional traction for the second edition of Circular sPrint was low. However, the reason for this might not be in marketing at all. The Circular sPrint events of 2021 were extended to two weeks compared to the one-week event of 2020. The longer duration may have complicated the participation of industry professionals who would have to sync the event both with their day job and family.

Monitoring the success of different marketing activities is possible through timestamps of the registrations and by simply asking in the application: “How did you learn about the event?”. Paid marketing campaigns would of course offer better control over the target group as well as in-depth statistics, if the project budget allows that.

Publishing day-to-day activities in social media during the event is also good practice to showcase the brainstorming and prototyping activities and event atmosphere. Some event content, such as lectures or an inspirational walkthrough of the fablab facilities, can be made publicly available as video recordings. This visibility can encourage participants and collaborators to take part in the next year’s event.

Participant Recruitment & Management

2.5.1. Intake Interview & Team Formation

A registration questionnaire and a participant interview ensure that the participant profile is a match with the event and that the expectations of both parties are aligned. In the Circular sPrint, a Google application form was embedded on the website and used to manage the registrations (see example in 4. Digital Appendices).

The intake interview can be organized, for example as a 30-45-minute meeting, either in person or remotely. Its primary goal is to form a personal tie between the organizers and an individual participant. We felt it was exceptionally important during the pandemic situation to offer this social interaction point already before the event. The intake interview should be made an interactive open discussion rather than an official, stiff interview. The point of the meeting is to briefly present what the event is about but most of all, let the participants present their own background and verbalize their own expectations and motivations for the event.

- Goals**
- Align the expectations of participants & the organizers
 - Collect information for later team formation
 - Provide a moment to ask questions
 - Reduce the risk of drop-outs

- Content**
- Explain the format and present the initial program

- What is expected from a participant: e.g., full time presence, prior knowledge, ...
- Participant presentation → Categorize the profile on a scale of knowledge on the themes of the event (For Circular sPrint: circularity, design thinking, 3D printing and CAD modeling)
- Present the Challenges, allow participants to express their preference
- Let the applicant themselves verify their interest to participate; *“Yes, I’m in”*

The applicant's skillset, personality, and their personal challenge preferences are used to decide which team and challenge the applicant is assigned to. Organizers should ensure each team has a balanced skillset for the challenge they will tackle. In Circular sPrint, we tried to assign at least a few people with 3D CAD and 3D printing experience in every 4-6-person team. This knowledge is crucial that every team has a chance for efficient prototyping. The rest of the members should diversify the team. It is helpful for the team if someone has deeper knowledge of the challenge topic, circular economy, and/or business modeling.

2.5.2. Communication & Timing

A large part of the participant's experience from an event is related to clear and timely communication. Everyone should know when and where to meet, what is the agenda, and what they are expected to work on and deliver next. Information should never contradict previous statements. Announced dates and times are to be respected as participants might need to plan their private life around them. The communication efforts start already by deciding the date when the event application opens and closes. Organizers should reserve a few weeks' time after the application closes for participant interviews and team formation. It is best to plan ahead and settle oneself in the position of a registered participant. What information do they have at each moment and what do they need?

- Lock the dates of the event well in advance (up to 1 year)
- Verify all information is correct on the website at the time of launch
- Plan **what** information and **when** to communicate for the registered participants
- Pre-event communication is best done via e-mail
- E-mail verification of the registrations (can be made automatic)
- Agreeing a date and a time for the intake interview
- Pre-event e-mail at the latest a few days before the event including the final schedule, first meeting time and location, or a remote meeting link
- The day-to-day communication during the event is better organized via faster means than email, for example creating groups in WhatsApp or Slack

- Post-event feedback survey via e-mail

Event Organization

2.6.1. Navigating Between a Physical, Hybrid, and a Virtual Event

The Circular sPrint can be conceived as an intensive, 1-2 week program taking place physically at a fablab or an experience taking place in a hybrid format. Physical events are preferred as they maximize learning and amplify the interaction between all the stakeholders. However, physical presence might not always be possible. Public health management restrictions, such as those caused by the Covid19 pandemic, may prevent the organization of an in-person version of an event from happening. For instance, the CRAFTH consortium had to adapt the Circular sPrint formats both in 2020 and 2021, to cope with the constraints brought by the pandemic. Nevertheless, consciously organizing a virtual or a hybrid event can also provide benefits. It can reach a considerably larger audience and foster new collaborations across national borders. Below we provide the overall structure and main advantages and disadvantages of three alternative event formats: 100% virtual event, hybrid event, and a hybrid event with distributed hubs.

VIRTUAL EVENT

The virtual event is included as an emergency back-up in case a similar situation, like a global pandemic, prevents from organizing in-person events. Participants, coaches, and industry stakeholders communicate and collaborate entirely on online platforms. Therefore, a quality video conferencing platform is quintessential for this event format to work (2.6.4. Event Infrastructure & Software). Figure 7 presents the program of the virtual Circular sPrint event 2020.

Figure 7. CRAFTH Circular sPrint 2020: virtual event program

Advantages

- Low logistic effort: no venue preparation, no travel, and no accommodation required
- Time efficient: coaches and participants do not need to travel back and forth to the venue
- Low cost

Disadvantages

- Participants will **not** remain concentrated throughout the day. Consider the following actions to keep the attention level high:
 - Split the program up; instead of 1 full week, consider a 2-week program with half days instead of full days.
 - Introduce short but intense lecture or activity blocks: each 50–60-minute block is followed by a 10- minute break.
 - Include physical activities or research actions that participants can undertake from their remote location.
- There is a risk that concepts will pivot to business models or service design due to restricted access to prototyping facilities.
- Online, group brainstorming using Miro, or other online platform, might not create the same group dynamics as brainstorming in real life would do.
- How do I prototype? Explore to what extent decentralized prototyping is an option.
 - Participants

- Does the participant own a 3D printer or is there a fablab nearby? (Be sure to ask this during the intake interview)
 - Sponsor the participants with 3D printing materials or get in contact with a fablab nearby.
 - Are the industry partners who submit a case able to do 3D printing?
-

HYBRID EVENT

Although a virtual event is not optimal for interaction, the CRAFTH consortium members do acknowledge that certain aspects of an online event increase efficiency, reduce workload and potentially reach a bigger target audience.

With the experience of Circular sPrint 2020 in mind, CRAFTH designed the 2021 edition of Circular sPrint into two parts, a two-week hybrid event.

The first part focuses on problem definition and ideation and takes place online. Participants will also follow several expert plenary sessions on circular design, additive manufacturing, and design thinking to familiarize them with the underlying technology, concepts, and the design process itself. Initial group brainstorming and coaching sessions also take place online. The first part could be further spread over multiple weeks. Allocating more time can allow participants to take up online tutorials on CAD modelling and the use of slicers for 3D printers and learn necessary skills for effective prototyping.

For the **second part**, participants move to a physical location where they put their ideas into practice using 3D printing. Concepts are tested. Results are presented at the end of this phase during a pitch and feedback session. Coaches will periodically provide feedback on the progress. The day-to-day interaction between participants in a prototyping and manufacturing environment is a catalyst for the design process. Try to keep the lab open as long as possible. Allow participants to continue working late and do not interrupt the flow.

Advantages

- It is possible to invite thematic experts for plenary sessions without asking them to travel to the venue.
- Hands on experience with additive manufacturing during the second part of the event.
- In person knowledge exchange during the second part of the event.

Disadvantages

- Increased logistic effort and related costs in comparison to a 100% online event.

- It is likely that you will recruit mostly local participants or those who can easily travel and accommodate themselves near the venue.
-

HYBRID EVENT WITH HUBS

A 100% online event is not tied to a geographic location. So, what if you want to run Circular sPrint with remote partners? This template for a hybrid event facilitates collaboration with remote hubs. In 2021 the Circular sPrint was organized simultaneously in Finland, Germany, and Belgium. These locations, or hubs, were individual events but also took advantage of the identical format. All online lecture content was shared between the events. Some challenges were tackled in multiple locations by separate teams.

For the first part of the event, the scenario remains the same as with the hybrid event: all stakeholders collaborate on a video conferencing platform.

For the second part of the event, CRAFTH advises to build in daily online sessions to maintain the connection between the various hubs. During the 2021 event, a daily “morning booster” was part of the program. Participants were assigned to bring their favourite morning drink, do a funny assignment etc. It was a great way to start the day and an opportunity to get to know each other better despite the distance. Similarly, at the end of each day, participants from every hub should visually present their activities for others.

Advantages

- Participants from different universities, countries, and regions can exchange experiences.
- Industry cases can be tackled by participants from different cultural backgrounds.
- Multiple teams can work on the same challenge from remote locations. The competitive aspect could result in higher quality outcomes.
- Plenary sessions can be followed by all participants spreading the workload among the organizers.

Disadvantages

- As the different hubs are physically separated, it may be hard to follow the progress in the other hubs.
- Regularly remind participants and coaches that online presence is required for the daily wrap-up sessions.
- Participants might get distracted and uninterested to follow the online content as most of the second part activities happen in the physical location.

Having the ideation tools online, participants might skip using them. Therefore, consider either reinforcing digital deliverables, or printing the design tools or templates. Be sure to scan and upload them into the digital platform daily so that the other hubs can follow on the daily

- progress.
-

2.6.2. Event Preparations & Human Resources

Running the Circular sPrint event once all preparations are done is a full-time job for at least two people. This counts the few final weeks before the event and the duration of the event itself. Practical arrangements are often small but surprisingly numerous and time-consuming. These last-minute activities include for example reserving and preparing facilities, generating online meeting invites, obtaining prototyping supplies, booking catering, interviewing participants, devising the final program, and communication to the participants and company representatives. Attendees might also have some questions at this point that require timely answers. During the event it is best to dedicate one person as the spokesperson who will handle all the presentations, daily wrap-ups, and communication. Experts will have their plenary sessions or coaching session at predetermined times. Agreeing on social media identifiers with organizers and the participants can boost the visibility of the event. Certain activities can be agreed beforehand to be shared in social media and included in the organizer's daily schedule, for example a team brainstorming board, the first prototype, final prototype, live coverage of a pitch, etc.

2.6.3. Example Event Program (Hybrid Event)

The initial program of the event should be known by the attendees already at the time of registration and the final program (only small edits) published latest a few weeks before the event starts. Also note that all the sessions requiring company representatives or coaching are agreed well in advance, preferably months before the event. Figure 8 displays the initial program of Circular sPrint 2021 that was published on the website at the time of registration. In the 2021 hybrid event, the first week was organized via virtual means and the second week in-person. The activities were split between lecture sessions and design sprint sessions. The final detailed program for the virtual CsP 2020 and hybrid event of 2021 are available in the online repository. In addition, company keynotes in the program can help further inspire and motivate attendees. As an example, a startup company [Yuma Labs held a keynote](#) on circular eyewear as part of Circular sPrint 2020.

Figure 8. Circular Sprint 2021 two-week program organized as a hybrid (with hubs) implementation.

2.6.4. Event Infrastructure & Software

Circular sPrint is fast paced and encompasses both brainstorming and prototyping as well as manufacturing. Provide participants a stimulating space where they will “live” and work for the duration of the sprint, preferably a fablab. A collaboration with a local fablab can be an option.

- It can get messy; embrace chaos
 - Give participants the possibility to put up post-it's everywhere.
 - Facilitate the projection of project ideas on screens or walls.
 - If possible, provide each team with a dedicated, private conference room for ideation between prototyping cycles.
- Provide space in proximity to the AM units as it is motivating to see the machines build your concept layer by layer. In case something does go wrong (print failing) it’s easy to respond without losing too much time.
- Provide space and equipment to post process the prints and to take further prototyping steps.
- Do you have a photo studio or corner on site? Document the process by making lots of videos and photos.

Figure 9. Prototyping at the Aalto University ADDLab with Ultimakers, Circular sPrint 2021.

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is the key technology of Circular sPrint. Whereas many hackathons focus on product concepts, business models, or low-level prototyping techniques, Circular sPrint should **always** strive to deliver AM fabricated prototypes as the tangible manifestation of the product - service concepts.

AM poses several challenges in terms of hardware and software. Having one person per team with a knowledge of CAD modeling is crucial as there is no time to teach this skill during the event. Slicing software on the other hand is pretty straightforward. A brief explanation is generally sufficient to slice a model for FDM, SLA or even SLS printing. For the more advanced techniques, one of the expert coaches should provide support for the teams.

AM CAPACITY, MAKERSPACES AND ONLINE COLLABORATION TOOLS

- AM is a relatively time-consuming process. Ensure there are sufficient machine capacity available. At a minimum we would advise allocating one dedicated FDM printer per team. In case you have additional FDM printers at your disposal, consider listing them in an online scheduler tool (for example as seen in Figure 10) or increasing the number of printers per team.

Why is this?

- Having more printers enable experiments with various materials, geometries, and concepts in parallel.

- Ensure that participants iterate on a design even while an “previous” concept is printing. The print farm should be constantly active during the prototyping phases.
- Give the participants the possibility to print multiple samples for testing purposes.

More advanced machinery: some machines might be more delicate to operate, require additional safety training, or come with expensive consumables → use a central planning tool to book these machines and have an experienced operator or coach set up the machine in collaboration with the participants. As an example, the metal 3D printer at the Aalto university was used together with the lab operator to 3D print one final prototype in stainless steel.

- Cap print duration as it might cause bottlenecks. How to do this?
 - Choose the right print parameters for the context → use the minimum viable setting for layer height, infill & support.
 - Schedule long prints overnight.
- Consider satellite manufacturing hubs to increase capacity. Once printed, the operator at the hub can evaluate the part and share findings with the participants.
- Test run and troubleshoot all equipment before the event.
- Planning is the key to success.

Figure 10. A 3D printer reservation calendar embedded into the Miro platform.

SOFTWARE

Challenge online ideation and documentation

Miro

Miro was our platform of choice to capture the flow of the design process. CRAFTH developed a Miro template which guides participants through the various steps of Circular sPrint. For future organizers we refer to the Miro boards (4. Digital Appendices) for more information.

Google Drive

Participants:

Bulk storage for all documents related to the project (research papers, photos of prototypes, CAD files etc.)

Company stakeholders might find it hard to figure out the Miro, so it's crucial to have participants set up a clear folder structure containing all the project outcomes.

Organizers: create folders with general info and team folders.

- General info: tutorials, CsP schedule & instructions, IP documents etc.
- Team folders: project briefing & background information related to the case.

CAD (Computer Aided Design)

CAD modelling software

Let participants work with the software they prefer. Speed is key, there is no time for them to learn CAD modelling during CsP.

If the participants lack CAD skills, it is advised to let them install CAD software prior to CsP so they can follow tutorials.

- Autodesk Fusion 360 ([link](#))
- Tinkercad ([link](#))

List the download links and tutorials in a Google Drive folder.

Slicers

Preferably use printers that come with a slicer which participants can install on their personal laptop. By the end of CsP participants should have a basic understanding of the AM workflow (CAD → STL/ OBJ/ ... → Slicer → Gcode for 3D printer).

Most desktop DIY FDM/ FFF printers are compatible with the free Ultimaker Cura software

<https://ultimaker.com/software/ultimaker-cura>

Settings > Printer > Add printer

Alternatives: Prusa slicer - [slic3er](#) –

Communication & outreach

Video conferencing

ZOOM was used both during the 2020 (online) & 2021 (hybrid) editions of Circular sPrint.

- Create one meeting for the complete duration of the sprint to simplify things.
- Keynote sessions open to the general public should be scheduled as a separate ZOOM meeting.
- Make breakout rooms for each team.

Eventbrite

In order to promote the event and raise awareness about circular economy, it is advised to host a keynote or plenary session for the board public. CRAFTH used Eventbrite ([link](#)) to manage the registration process.

2.6.5. Coaching

It is important to guide participants in a structured way through the Circular sPrint. Provide internal coaches who are experts in the themes of the event that the participants meet briefly at a regular basis to discuss their progress or any issues (for example twice a day). Additionally, provide 2-3 feedback moments with the challenge owners (companies) at a few fixed moments. At beginning of the sprint, the company gives the challenge brief, in the middle they provide feedback on the progress, and at the end of the project the results are transferred to the company. At that point, the company will give their final feedback to the team on the outcome of the project.

Dos and don'ts:

- Coaches can be assigned by topic (ex. 3D-printing expert, Circular economy expert, design process expert) or per team (one coach guiding one or multiple teams). A combination of both can also work. Make clear decisions on this before starting the circular sPrint and be

very clear on communicating who the participants can reach out to. Coaching times should be clearly marked in the daily schedule!

- Steer the participants in following the structure of the Circular sPrint, participants might be new to a design sprint process. It might help to be strict on following the sprint structure for example at the end of a phase (or a day) a clear deliverable outcome has to be presented during the feedback moment.
- Plan fixed coaching moments of 15 min to 30 min where feedback can be given, provide enough time for the participants to experiment on their own too, and don't bother or steer them too often during their working time.
- Coaches can inspire and help the team in ideation but sometimes a decision has to be made. As a coach, avoid giving converging and diverging feedback at the same time. Having too many opinions and possible development directions can completely puzzle the team. If the time is running low to finish a deliverable, gently push the team to choose their preferred idea or prototyping direction and stick with it.

2.6.6. Social Aspects & Team Spirit

Humans are innately social animals. Social interaction and unofficial discussion are an intrinsic, but underrated part of all innovation programs. Being able to talk with others, even for a short while, without a clear incentive was in high demand, especially when the Circular sPrint was organized virtually during the covid19 pandemic. Favorable conditions for interaction should be hard-wired in the event program and all arrangements. This is done simply by reserving time for the team members to get to know each other. In addition, time should be reserved for questions and unstructured discussion. Our solution in the virtual event was to organize every morning a so-called “morning booster”. Attendees were divided randomly into breakout rooms and given a mundane task or topic to get the discussion started. Promoting the social aspects of an event is obviously a lot easier during a physical event. In the Aalto hybrid Circular sPrint of 2021, a relaxed BBQ session ended each day of intense prototyping. In addition, a pre-event was organized where the participants had a chance to meet one day before the official program started. This can help initiate the team spirit and reduce the likelihood of dropouts.

2.7.2. Circular Design Tools

When including circularity aspects in the design of a product or service, several tools may inform and inspire participants to evaluate possible pathways:

- www.circulator.eu is a tool that provides examples of circular business models for each combination of the following relevant dimensions:
 - Circular Value Creation: what do you do to increase circularity?
 - Strong Value Proposition: how do you convince your customers?
 - Circular Value Network: how and with whom do you cooperate?
- Inspiration for the use of circular strategies can be found in some **circular economy scans** that address questions on value retention throughout the life-cycle of a product. In our sprint, we combined insights from several tools, including the CEvaluator ([link](#)) and Ecopreneur ([link](#))
- A **Value Network Map** is a tool that invites you to map every single stage of the value network of your product or service, including its surrounding ecosystem. First, you could reconstruct the current business case, and next, you are invited to assess the impact of circular strategies throughout the value network.
- Once ideas to include circular strategies have been identified, and the value network has been mapped, it is important to evaluate the **incentive compatibility** for each strategy. In other words: to what extent and in what way are interests and incentives aligned between several players throughout the value chain when you apply a circular economy strategy. This mainly involves suppliers, customers, but also stakeholders within the company (e.g., product managers, operations, marketing and sales, procurement, Board of Directors, ...).
- Very general tools to complete the underlying business model are the **Business Model Canvas** ([link](#)) and the **Lean Start-up Canvas** ([link](#)). Several adapted versions of both tools are developed to include sustainability or circularity aspects. The basic challenge, however, remains to combine circular strategies with a strong value proposition. Therefore, a **Value Proposition Canvas** ([link](#)) can be used:
- Last but not least, the **Sustainable Development Goals** ([link](#)) can be an inspiration to look into sustainable circular solutions. In our approach, we see circularity as a means to contribute to sustainable development, and not as a blind quest to extend the lifetime of materials to eternity.

In the condensed program of a Circular Sprint, it will be impossible to master and use all these tools. However, it will be interesting to introduce at least some of them, such that participants have access to a toolbox that may include fit-for-purpose instruments for the case they are working on.

3. DISCUSSION

In the final chapter, we discuss our learnings of the CRAFTH project and the Circular sPrint event. We elaborate on ways how the events could be improved in the future based on the feedback gathered. Finally, we discuss how similar innovation initiatives could become economically independent and continue once the project funding ends.

The main goal of Circular sPrint is to promote circular economy with new solutions through design thinking and technology. In other words, the event has a larger societal goal that transcends past any of the individual challenges or final prototypes. We wish to reroute the thinking patterns of participants from a purely for-profit capitalistic view more towards sustainable development. However, such a goal is very hard to measure. How did the event succeed? The number of attendees and participants at the side events can be measured to assess the reach of the event. This is one way to measure at least the educational impact. Tracking how (and if) companies have implemented any changes to their existing products or processes, is harder. We propose asking this directly from all the participating companies in short surveys, for example 6 months after the event. In addition, inviting challenge owners from previous years' events as keynote speakers is an opportunity to hear about possible changes in more detail.

To improve the impact of the event, we recommend starting with the companies early on. Does the challenge definition make sense to begin with? What would be the most impactful problem to solve from the sustainability perspective? It may be good to organize a brainstorming session together with a circular economy specialist to outline the challenge definition. Calculating a life cycle assessment (LCA) for the existing solution before the event, and for the solution found in the event at the end, allows for direct comparison. However, this might require access to data that the company does not wish to reveal due to its confidentiality. Similarly, getting access to 3D models, supply chain information, material definitions, etc. can help the team in providing the best solution for a given challenge. Consider signing a non-disclosure agreement between the organizing body, the company, and the team members working on the particular challenge.

Creating a new innovation contest is a resource-intensive endeavor. To maximize the return of investment, it makes sense to ensure the program will continue once it has been created. However, if innovation contest initiatives are often based on one-time funding, how could the continuity of an event be secured?

In our opinion, the organizing body will need to be defined and anchored already in the planning face of the project. Otherwise, once the money runs out, the motivation will also run out. The

agreed “anchor organizer” could be, for example, a university, a company, or an innovation agency. Nevertheless, they should have a clear benefit (regardless of one-time project funding) and motivation to continue the same initiative also in the future. In the university context this could mean that the innovation contest will become a part of an annual course. For a company such an event may be motivated by promoting internal innovation and acquiring fresh talent as an internal innovation contest. Lastly, innovation agencies could act as the implementing body. The motivation for them is to tie the contest together with their brand and make it an annual occasion to contact new project and B2B partners.

Now that there is an “anchor organizer” for a yearly event, different funding strategies can be discussed. If the event is organized as part of a course or within a company, the funding could be negotiated to the annual teaching, or company R&D budget. This allows the event to remain free for the participants. Another funding strategy may be based on an entry fee for participants. A better revenue flow can be created by charging the participating companies only. Asking a fee from individual participants (who are often students and not in the best financial situation) may considerably reduce the pool of potential attendees. If a fee is requested from the companies who participate in a challenge, the cost naturally needs to align with the company expectations. What do they wish to benefit from the event? Is the fee justifiable in relation to the expected outcomes? For a few-week program, a realistic fee could be from 500€ up to 3000€. The cost could differ depending on the size of the company as smaller start-ups rarely have the financial capacity (Yet, they may have more resources to invest in personally coaching the team). With an event that consists of 4-6 challenges, a realistic operational budget range is from 5000€ to 10 000€. This amount should cover the prizes, infrastructure, marketing, and a few person-months of work (for an already established innovation contest).

Another very common way how innovation contests and hackathons are organized is by using, at least partially, volunteer work. This approach may be enticing once the event format has already gathered enough momentum. The higher the brand-value of an event, the easier this strategy is to implement. Volunteers can help reduce operational costs and will often automatically help the event through word-of-mouth marketing. For volunteers, the money is not relevant but they will still need some form of compensation. The reason to participate may be very personal and vary from one volunteer to another. They may be inspired by a prior participation to the same event, or just want to acquire new contacts. Volunteering is always a possibility to learn about event organization but the motivation can simply be to socialize with a familiar community or like-minded people. In the best-case scenario, the volunteers will form an idealistic, rotating community who shares the same interests and wants to ensure the continuity of the event. The organizers have then managed to create a self-sustaining movement. And a rolling stone is easier to keep moving.

4. DIGITAL APPENDICES

Throughout the text we refer to files created as part of the CRAFTH-project and for the Circular sPrint events. These documents are published (open access) in an online repository for anyone to use and draw inspiration from. All files are stored in the Zenodo database maintained by CERN data center. The files can be accessed through the DOI identifier:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6327728>

Contents of the data package:

- Circular sPrint Playbook
- Circular sPrint 2021 Timeline
- The Innovation Challenge Design Canvas (Empty)
- The Innovation Challenge Design Canvas (Circular sPrint)
- Application Questions
- Circular sPrint Website
- Circular sPrint One Pager
- Circular sPrint LinkedIn Card
- Circular sPrint Challenge Card
- Example: Company Agreement
- Example: Participant Terms & Conditions
- Circular sPrint Program Overview
- Final Program Circular sPrint
- Miro Template Circular sPrint 2021